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Contents

Contents	3
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	7
List of Acronyms	8
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
Title of Deliverable	10
1 Introduction	10
2 Instrumentation	11
2.1 The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN)	11
2.1.1 GEometry ANd Tracking (GEANT) computation of the energy response of Solid State Detector (SSD) F	11
2.1.2 Influence of the spacecraft environment	12
2.1.3 EPHIN aboard SOHO	13
2.1.4 EPHIN aboard Chandra	14
2.1.5 GEANT simulations of EPHIN aboard Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) and Chandra	15
2.1.6 Comparison of SOHO and Chandra data with Alpha Magnet Spectrometer (AMS)-02 fluxes	16
2.2 Solar Orbiter (SoIO) Energetic Particle Detector (EPD) High Energy Telescope (HET)	30
2.2.1 The HET Instrument	30
2.2.2 GEANT simulations of the HET	31
2.2.3 Comparison to other spacecraft measurements	33
3 Conclusions	40
Bibliography	41
Appendix	43

List of Figures

1	Sketch (left) and realization in the GEANT model (right) of the EPHIN instrument, adapted from Kühl et al. (2020) and Köberle et al. (2024).	11
2	Energy response of SSD-F for an isotropic flux of protons without (blue curve), including the SOHO (green curve) and Chandra (red curve) spacecraft, respectively.	12
3	Left: Sketch of SOHOs spacecraft and its instruments (EPHINs is part of Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer (COSTEP) suite); Right: The EPHIN model and the spacecraft proxy with a half-sphere aluminum shielding.	13
4	Temperature and count rates of the single detectors of SOHO/EPHIN.	14
5	Left: Sketch of Chandra spacecraft and its instruments; Right: The EPHIN model and the spacecraft proxy using a new scheme with a half-sphere aluminum shielding.	15
6	Count rates of the single detectors of Chandra/EPHIN for January 2000.	16
7	Distribution of counts in SSD-B measured by EPHIN aboard Chandra in 2000. Shown are only counts below 1000. A fit to the data by a Gaussian is superseded. Values for which $counts_B < \mu + 3\sigma$ are considered to be quiet times, when no Solar Energetic Particles (SEPs) have a major impact on the count rate of SSD F.	17
8	The upper panel shows the time series of daily averaged count rates obtained by SSD F aboard SOHO using quiet time periods (for details see text). The middle panels display the proton and helium flux measured by AMS-02 at a rigidity $R = 2.15$ GV and the lower panel the variation of the modulation potential given by Väisänen et al. (2023).	18
9	Count rate of SSD F aboard SOHO as function of the sum of the proton and helium fluxes $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for rigidities $R_{low} = 1.71$ GV to $R_{low} = 2.97$ GV. Curves are from left to right for $R = 2.97$ GV, $R = 2.67$ GV, $R = 2.4$ GV, $R = 2.15$ GV, $R = 1.92$ GV and $R = 1.71$ GV (for details see text in Sec.2.1.6.)	19
10	Count rate ratio of SSD F aboard SOHO and sum of the proton and helium fluxes $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for rigidities $R_{low} = 1.71$ GV to $R_{low} = 3.4$ GV, respectively. Curves are from top to bottom for $R = 2.97$ GV, $R = 2.67$ GV, $R = 2.4$ GV, $R = 2.15$ GV, $R = 1.92$ GV and $R = 1.71$ GV (for details see text in Sec.2.1.6.)	19
11	Normalized ratio $r_N = \frac{c_{SSD-F}}{\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}}(R_{low})$. The correlation coefficient C.C and the fit parameter of a quadratic fit are shown in the inlets of each panel. The panels show from left to right and to to bottom the ratios for $R_{low} = \{1.71, 1.92, 2.15, 2.4, 2.67, 2.97\}$. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.	21
12	From top to bottom normalized count rates of EPHIN aboard SOHO to the sum of fluxes of protons and helium for rigidities at 1.71 GV, 1.92 GV and 2.15 GV measured by AMS-2 (for details see text in Sec.2.1.6).	22
13	From top to bottom are shown the ratio of (SSD F-2034)/ $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ at $R = 1.71$ GV and the flux of $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ and the normalized count rate of (SSD F-2034) from 2011 to 2019. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.	23
14	Ratio $r = \frac{c_{SSD-F} - c_0}{\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}}(R_{low})$. c_0 is given in the title of each panel. The panels show from left to right and to to bottom the ratios for $R_{low} = \{1.71, 1.92, 2.15\}$. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.	24

15	Ratio $r = \frac{c_{SSD-F} - c_0}{\Phi_p} (R_{low})$. c_0 is given in the title of each panel. The panels show from left to right and to to bottom the ratios for $R_{low} = \{1.0, 1.16, 1.33, 1.51, 1.71, 192\}$. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.	25
16	From top to bottom are shown the ratio of (SSD F-2846)/ Φ_p at $R = 1.33$ GV and the flux of Φ_p and the normalized count rate of (SSD F-2846) from 2011 to 2019. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.	26
17	The left and right panel show in the upper panels the normalized count rate of SSD-F aboard SOHO $c_{SSD-F,Soho}$ and Chandra $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$ and in the lower panel the ratio of $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$ to $c_{SSD-F,SOHO}$, respectively. The left and the right panel are identical for time periods before 2005.3 and after 2008 (for details see text in Sec.2.1.6).	28
18	Ratio of $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$ to $c_{SSD-F,SOHO}$ as function of the average count rate $c_{av} = (c_{SSD-F,SOHO} + c_{SSD-F,Chandra})/2$ (for details see text).	28
19	SOLO-HET	30
20	Schematic diagram of the HET sensor head. Exemplary particle trajectories ending up in different data products are shown by the arrows: stopping in B (red), stopping in C (green), penetrating (blue), GCR channel (aquamarine), C single counter (orange). From (?)	31
21	GEANT4 visualization of the HET sensor head surrounded by the spacecraft model of SoLO in the model introduced by ? and this work in the left and right panel, respectively. . .	32
22	Preliminary simulation results for single detector response functions of protons, alphas and electrons for detection thresholds of 4 and 10 MeV deposited in the BGO with and without spacecraft model.	33
23	Preliminary simulation results for Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCR) trigger response functions of protons, alphas and electrons in two channels of 15 to 30 and 30 to 56 MeV deposited in the Bismuth germanium oxide (BGO) with and without spacecraft model. The horizontal dashed line marks the analytical geometry factor. For clarity the legend, valid for all panels, is only shown in the middle panel.	33
24	Countrates of HET Flight Model (FMO)1 from early 2020 until 2025. a) HET single detector counter High Gain (HG) original data (blue) and quiet times (red). b) HET single detector counter Low Gain (LG) original data (blue) and quiet times (orange). c) comparison of quiet times measurement of HET and SOHO/EPHIN single detector counters. d) HET GCR-trigger 0 HG original data (blue) and quiet times (purple). e) HET GCR-trigger 1 original data (blue) and quiet times (magenta). f) comparison of quiet times measurements of HET GCR trigger and SOHO/EPHIN single detector counter.	34
25	Left: daily averaged countrates of the HG channel of HET FMO1 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F. . .	35
26	Top left: daily averaged countrates of the GCR-0 channel of HET FMO1 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Top right: same but times excluded where $T < -10^\circ$. Bottom panels: respective ratios.	37
27	Daily averaged countrate of the GCR-0 channel in purple and temperature of the HET instrument in black. Solid lines show FMO1 and dotted lines FMO2. For clarity 2 counts/minute were added to FMO2.	38
28	The left panel of the figure displays the count rate in GCR-1 as function of SOHO/EPHIN. The right panel displays the ratio of GCR-1/SSD-F over SSD-F.	38

29 Countrates of HET FMO2 from early 2020 until 2025. **a)** HET single detector counter HG original data (blue) and quiet times (red). **b)** HET single detector counter LG original data (blue) and quiet times (orange). **c)** comparison of quiet times measurement of HET and SOHO/EPHIN single detector counters. **d)** HET GCR-trigger 0 HG original data (blue) and quiet times (purple). **e)** HET GCR-trigger 1 original data (blue) and quiet times (magenta). **f)** comparison of quiet times measurements of HET GCR trigger and SOHO/EPHIN single detector counter. 43

30 Left: daily averaged countrates of the HG channel of HET FMO2 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F. . . 44

31 Left: daily averaged countrates of the LG channel of HET FMO2 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F. . . 44

32 Left: daily averaged countrates of the GCR-0 channel of HET FMO2 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F. 45

33 Left: daily averaged countrates of the GCR-1 channel of HET FMO2 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F. 45

List of Tables

- 1 AMS energy Ranges for Protons and Helium from Aguilar et al. (2023a) used in our analysis. 20
- 2 Linear fit parameters for cross calibration of the two HET instruments and SOHO/EPHIN. Given are the values for the two single detector channels and the two GCR channels respectively. Uncertainties of the slopes are neglected. *Values calculated for GCR-0 channel for FMO 1 are given for temperatures $> -10^{\circ}$ 36

List of Acronyms

AMS	Alpha Magnet Spectrometer
BGO	Bismuth germanium oxide
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CAU	Christian-Albrechts-Universität
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
COSTEP	Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer
EPD	Energetic Particle Detector
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
EPT	Electron Proton Telescope
ESA	European Space Agency
FD	Forbush Decrease
FFS	Force field solution
FMO	Flight Model
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Rays
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
GMIR	Global Merged Interaction Region
HET	High Energy Telescope
ICME	Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection
L1	Lagrange Point 1
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NM	Neutron Monitor
SC	spacecraft
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SF	Solar Flare
SIS	SupraThermal Ion Spectrograph
SOAR	Solar Orbiter Archive
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArTicle Data
SSD	Solid State Detector
STEP	SupraThermal Protons and alpha
SWA	Solar Wind Analyser
HG	High Gain
LG	Low Gain
CIR	Corotating Interaction Region

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report explores the potential insights gained from single-count measurements of Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCRs) on [SOHO](#) and Chandra [EPHIN](#) and SolO/[HET](#). The focus is on the statistical, physical, and environmental interpretations of these measurements and their implications for astrophysics, space weather prediction, and radiation monitoring.

Specifically, the single detector counters [SSD-F](#) of [EPHIN](#) onboard Chandra and [SOHO](#) are compared to published [AMS-02](#) measurements until 2019 to establish a well calibrated baseline which is then used to compare with SolO/[HET](#) measurements from early 2020 until 2025.

A good agreement between the single detector counters is found, and cross-calibration functions are given.

1 Introduction

Single-count rate measurements refer to the detection of particles (i.e. photons, electrons, protons, heavier ions) in a single detector that are counted if the signal is above a given threshold, offering investigations on cosmic ray activity. In this report, the focus is on individual particle events identified in the time series of single count measurements. The most important contribution to such measurements come from:

- **GCRs** that are high-energy particles originating outside the Solar System, primarily from supernova explosions and other energetic astrophysical processes (see for example [Blasi 2013](#); [Gabici et al. 2019](#), and citation therein).
- **SEPs** that are energetic particles accelerated by Solar Flares (**SFs**) or Coronal Mass Ejections (**CMEs**) (see for example [Reames 2024](#); [Whitman et al. 2023](#); [Vlahos et al. 2019](#); [Klein & Dalla 2017](#), and references therein)

Key Insights from Single-Count Measurements Single-count rate measurements provide data to estimate:

- The flux of cosmic rays at a given location.
- The energy spectrum of **GCRs**, when combined with the detector sensitivity and the simple one-parameter model provided by the Force field solution (**FFS**) ([Moraal 2013](#)).

By tracking single counts over time, we can study:

- Solar modulation effects on **GCRs**.
- Short-term variations due to **SEPs** or Forbush Decreases (**FDs**).

Methodology Single-count measurements typically involve:

- Use of scintillators, proportional counters, as utilized in Neutron Monitors (**NMs**), or semiconductor detectors.
- Calibration and correction for environmental factors, such as the environment of the spacecraft.

Single-count measurements of cosmic rays and energetic particles, despite their simplicity, provide a wealth of information about space radiation, and space weather.

2 Instrumentation

2.1 The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN)

The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN, Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) is part of the COSTEP suite onboard SOHO. A schematic view of the EPHIN instrument together with its realization in the GE-

Figure 1: Sketch (left) and realization in the GEANT model (right) of the EPHIN instrument, adapted from Kühl et al. (2020) and Köberle et al. (2024).

ometry AND Tracking (GEANT) model is shown in Fig. 1. The instrument consists of a stack of six SSDs (labeled A-F in Fig. 1) that is surrounded by a scintillation detector (G), which acts as an anticoincidence. Stopping ions are identified by applying the $\frac{dE}{dx} - E$ -method. Since the data rate is limited, energy losses in detectors A-E can only be transmitted for a statistical ensemble of all particles counted by EPHIN. A crude separation between electrons, protons, and helium has been introduced for different penetration depths, that is, different coincidences, by introducing different energy-loss thresholds in SSD A (for details see Müller-Mellin et al. 1995). To monitor time-dependent instrumental issues, various parameters are recorded independently of any coincidence condition, including the sensor and electronic box temperatures, leakage currents, and count rates of the six SSDs (A to F) and the anticoincidence scintillator (G) of EPHIN.

2.1.1 GEANT computation of the energy response of SSD F

Heber et al. (2015) have shown that EPHIN is capable of monitoring count rate variations with amplitudes in the below 1% regime on an hourly time resolution and hence, observe FD associated to small Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection (ICME). They used the hourly averaged variation of the SSD F. In the study by Belov et al. (2021) 421 FDs were investigated using SSD F. During solar minimum SSD F has a typical counting rate of more than 10^4 counts/min. While being superior in terms of statistics and time resolution compared to the coincidence channels, single counters do have the deficit of lacking any direct information about the energy deposition of measured particles and directionality. The GEANT-4 model of EPHIN can be used to determine the energy response of SSD F for protons, helium and electrons. Following Kühl et al. (2015a) we compute the energy response of SSD F for protons in the energy range

Figure 2: Energy response of [SSD-F](#) for an isotropic flux of protons without (blue curve), including the [SOHO](#) (green curve) and [Chandra](#) (red curve) spacecraft, respectively.

from above 10 MeV/amu to 100 GeV/amu using the Geometry Description Markup Language ([GDML](#)) model of [EPHIN](#) given in deliverable D2.1 (for details see [Köberle et al. 2024](#)) and an isotropic angular distribution (for computation principle of the response function see [Sullivan 1971](#), and references to this paper): The geometric factor G for [SSD F](#) with radius $r = 4$ cm was computed following [Sullivan \(1971\)](#):

$$G = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot A = 2 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot r^2 \quad (1)$$

With $r = 4$ cm follows $G_{SSD_F} \approx 316$ cm² sr. [Fig. 2](#) displays the computed energy dependence for protons for [EPHIN](#) only, aboard the [SOHO](#) and [Chandra](#) spacecraft by the blue, green and red lines, respectively. From that figure it is evident that the minimum proton energy is about 50 MeV to trigger [SSD F](#) independently of the spacecraft mounting. Below this energy particles are stopped in the surrounding material. Above ~ 130 MeV (see the dotted vertical red line in [Fig. 2](#)) all trajectories reach [SSD F](#) and a value in agreement with the geometric factor is found until secondary particle production sets in. The green and red curves will be discussed below.

2.1.2 Influence of the spacecraft environment

[EPHIN](#) was mounted onboard the Solar and Heliospheric Observatory ([SOHO](#)) and onboard [Chandra](#). For a single detector count rate of e.g. [SSD F](#) particles from all directions contribute to it. Thus it is essential to include a model of the spacecraft into the [GEANT](#) simulation as described in [Köberle et al. \(2024\)](#):

- As a first step a simplified model of the spacecraft with given dimensions is implemented in the simulation with the location of the instrument given in the left panels of [Fig. 3](#) and [5](#) for [SOHO](#) and [Chandra](#), respectively.
- A simplified "ray tracing" simulation with so-called [GEANTINOS](#) was performed to determine the path length for a non interacting particle passing through the spacecraft. The mass distribution is computed over 4π in steps of 5 degrees.

Figure 3: Left: Sketch of SOHO's spacecraft and its instruments (EPHINs is part of COSTEP suite); Right: The EPHIN model and the spacecraft proxy with a half-sphere aluminum shielding.

- This mass distributions are used to scale the density of an aluminum decoy in each given direction. This way, a somewhat "variable thickness" half sphere as a spacecraft proxy was obtained as shown in the right panels of Fig. 3 and 5, respectively.

This is quite important because EPHIN is mounted on one of the edges of the SOHO and Chandra spacecraft, leading to some directions in the field of view being far less obstructed by the passive matter of the spacecraft than others.

2.1.3 EPHIN aboard SOHO

The Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) is a joint mission by the European Space Agency (ESA) and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) (for details Domingo et al. 1995, and references therein). Launched on December 2, 1995 its final destination was an orbit around Lagrange Point 1 (L1), approximately 1.5 million kilometers from Earth, allowing continuous observation of the Sun. Its primary objective is to study the Sun from its core to its outer corona and the solar wind. In detail:

- Investigate the structure and dynamics of the solar interior.
- Study the outer solar atmosphere, including the corona and transition region.
- Analyze the solar wind and its interaction with the interplanetary medium.
- Investigate the sources and acceleration of Solar Energetic Particles (SEPs).

For that purpose it is equipped with 12 scientific instruments, which are broadly categorized into three groups of which one are instruments for in-situ measurements of solar wind and energetic particles. One of them is the Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN) that is described above. The location of the instrument is shown in the left panel of Fig. 3 with the approximation by a shell model as described above.

Figure 4: Temperature and count rates of the single detectors of SOHO/EPHIN.

Among others EPHIN provides single detector count rates for all detectors (A00, B00, to G) that are shown in Figure 4 together with the temperature of the EPHIN electronic box (upper panel) for the mission since 1996.

Although sudden increases in all detectors can be related to SEP events and the 11-year variations seen in the count rates of detectors B, F and G correspond to the GCR modulation, other signatures give insights on the technical condition of the different detectors. The anti coincidence scintillator (G) as well as SSD B and F show no change in behavior during the course of the mission, the count rate of SSD A, the first detector at the very top of the stack, clearly shows a correlation with the annual temperature variations of the instrument from around 2003. The count rates of the SSDs E and D have increased by orders of magnitude due to detector noise around 1997 and 2013, respectively. To account for these issues, the EPHIN instrument was switched to failure modes on October 31, 1996 and October 4, 2017, respectively. The failure modes prevent dead-time issues due to the electronic noise but are reducing the energy resolution, i.e. the nominal four proton channels are merged into three and two channels, respectively. The count rate of the SSD C is increasing more gradually in the last decades, but is still below critical conditions.

2.1.4 EPHIN aboard Chandra

The *Chandra X-ray Observatory*, launched by NASA on July 23, 1999, is one of the most powerful X-ray telescopes ever built. It is part of NASA's Great Observatories program. Named after the Nobel laureate Subrahmanyan Chandrasekhar, Chandra provides unprecedented insight into high-energy processes

Figure 5: Left: Sketch of Chandra spacecraft and its instruments; Right: The **EPHIN** model and the spacecraft proxy using a new scheme with a half-sphere aluminum shielding.

and phenomena in the universe by:

- Studying high-energy regions of the universe, such as black holes, supernova remnants, and galaxy clusters.
- Exploring the physics of dark matter, dark energy, and the evolution of cosmic structures.
- Detecting and characterizing X-ray emissions from stars, galaxies, and other celestial bodies.

EPHIN has been installed aboard the Chandra X-ray Observatory because Chandra's orbit crosses the radiation belts. Since it is designed to monitor the particle environment in space, it provides valuable data on the flux and composition of energetic charged particles, including electrons, protons, and helium nuclei and was used to warn the science instruments about high radiation levels. As for **EPHIN** aboard **SOHO** Chandra/**EPHIN** provides single detector count rates for all detectors (A00, B00, to G) that are shown in the left panel of Figure 6 for January 1 to 12, 2000. The right panel of the figure displays the orbit of the spacecraft around the Earth together with the Van Allen and electron radiation belts. Since the orbit of the spacecraft is about 63 hours and 29 minutes with a perigee of about 14.528 km Chandra crosses the radiation belts regularly, as can be seen by the increase of all single detector count rates. This high radiation exposure led to the fact that the anti coincidence scintillator G and detector A were switched off in December 2007 and 2008, respectively. From that period onward, Chandra scientists decided to point to directions in the sky that led to an exposure of **EPHIN** to Sun light with the consequence that the temperature rises above given limits. The instrument was switched off in 2014.

2.1.5 GEANT simulations of **EPHIN** aboard **SOHO** and Chandra

Following the approach described in Sec.2.1.1, the energy response of **SSD F** is computed including the spacecraft structure as described in Köberle et al. (2024) and Kühl et al. (2015a). Fig. 3 and Fig. 5 displays the current **GEANT4** model based on the **GDML** description of the instrument aboard **SOHO** and Chandra, respectively (for details see Köberle et al. 2024). The simulations were performed for protons in the energy range from 10 MeV/amu to 100 GeV/amu and for electrons between 500 keV and 20 MeV. The energy distribution was chosen to be a power law $\phi(E) = \phi_0 \cdot E^{-1}$ with an isotropic particle direction.

Figure 6: Count rates of the single detectors of Chandra/EPHIN for January 2000.

For each run $n = 10^9$ particles were tracked resulting in the energy responses for protons as displayed by the green and red curves for SOHO and Chandra in Fig. 2, respectively. The geometric factor of $G = 316 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sr}$ is indicated by the dashed lines. In comparison to the simulation for EPHIN only the expected geometric factor is reached at energies of about 200 MeV and 300 MeV for EPHIN aboard SOHO and Chandra, respectively. Thus the shielding by the spacecraft lead to large differences in the energy response at energies between a few tenth of MeV to 300 MeV and above a GeV when secondary particle production contributes significantly to the energy response. However, a detailed discussion of the results will be given in deliverable D 2.3.

2.1.6 Comparison of SOHO and Chandra data with AMS-02 fluxes

The single detector counter SSD-F measure the flux of all particles for which the energy loss is above a threshold energy loss $\Delta E > 150 \text{ keV}$ (for details see Sierks 1997; Kühl et al. 2015b, 2020, and references therein). Because the AMS collaboration has only published daily averaged data excluding SEP events the following comparison can only performed for quiet time periods. These periods are defined for the single counters from SOHO and Chandra by analyzing the yearly distribution of counts measured in SSD-B. SSD-B is sensitive to low energy electrons and protons leading to count rate increases measured during SEP events (similar to the method described in Kühl et al. 2016). As an example Fig. 7 shows the distribution of counts/minute measured in 2000 by EPHIN aboard Chandra. The distribution was fitted by a Gaussian function for $counts_B < 1000/\text{min}$. $counts_B < (\mu + 3\sigma)/\text{min}$ are considered to define quiet times, when no SEPs have a major impact on the count rate of SSD F. Fig. 8 shows the daily averaged count rates of SSD-F in the upper panel for quiet time periods. During such periods the energy flux spectrum can be approximated by solutions of the force field solution with the modulation potential Φ as describing parameter (a detailed derivation and discussion of galactic cosmic ray propagation can be found in Moraal 2013; Potgieter 2013, and references therein). Elements contributing to the flux of GCRs are protons and helium. Higher Z material and electrons are contributing less than a few percent to the total flux. Therefore we used the daily averaged proton and Helium fluxes from the AMS-02 instrument published by Aguilar et al. (2021) and Aguilar et al. (2022). AMS-02 provides the flux of protons and helium in different rigidity bins in the range from 1.0 to above 100 GV for protons and 1.7 GV to 100 GV for helium.

Figure 7: Distribution of counts in **SSD-B** measured by **EPHIN** aboard Chandra in 2000. Shown are only counts below 1000. A fit to the data by a Gaussian is superseded. Values for which $counts_B < \mu + 3\sigma$ are considered to be quiet times, when no **SEPs** have a major impact on the count rate of **SSD F**.

The two middle panel of the figure show the flux of protons and protons plus helium, and helium at a rigidity $r = 2.15$ GV taken from [Aguilar et al. \(2023a\)](#). The lower panel displays the modulation potential taken from [Väisänen et al. \(2023\)](#). The trend of the solar modulation is visible in all panels with two minima in the particle flux measurements in 2014 and 2015 due to the Gnevyshev effect (see for example [Gnevyshev 1967](#), and references therein). During solar maximum, an enhancement in cosmic ray fluxes is seen before the flux declines towards a second minimum. The effect is most properly associated with the complex restructuring of the Sun's magnetic field, which occurs around solar maximum when the solar magnetic field switches its polarity from an so-called $A < 0$ solar magnetic epoch to an $A > 0$ one leading to charge sign dependent modulation observed in the temporal variation of electron and proton fluxes (see for example [Aguilar et al. 2023b](#), and references therein). [Janardhan et al. \(2018\)](#) found that the solar coronal magnetic field changed its polarity in Nov. 2014 to a so called $A > 0$ -solar magnetic epoch that is defined when the magnetic north and south pole correspond with the northern and southern hemisphere, respectively. From 2015 onward all particle fluxes are increasing with the exception of the strong solar activity period in 2017: In September 2017, the Sun exhibited significant activity associated with a series of **CMEs** that propagated through the heliosphere. As these **CMEs** traveled outward in the heliosphere, they modulated the flux of galactic cosmic rays (**GCRs**) reaching Earth. This effect is especially prominent when the different **CMEs** interact with each other forming a Global Merged Interaction Region (**GMIR**) (details in [McDonald et al. 1993](#), and references therein). [Guo et al. \(2021\)](#) reported that such situation was present during the September 2017 period leading to the monthly depression in the **GCR** flux. These variation is also reflected in the temporal variation of the modulation potential derived from Neutron Monitor (**NM**) by [Väisänen et al. \(2023\)](#) shown in the lower panel of Fig. 8. From the published **AMS 02** data set we used for our analysis the lowest rigidity range provided by [Aguilar et al. \(2023a\)](#) as listed in Tab. 1 from $R_{low} = 1.71$ GV to $R_{low} = 2.97$ GV. Note that **AMS** does not provide Helium fluxes for rigidities lower than 1.71 GV.

Fig. 9 shows the measured count rate of **SSD-F** c_{SSD-F} by **SOHO EPHIN** as function of the sum of the **AMS** proton and helium fluxes $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for rigidities $R_{low} = 1.71$ GV to $R_{low} = 2.97$ GV. Curves are from left to right for $R = 2.97$ GV, $R = 2.67$ GV, $R = 2.4$ GV, $R = 2.15$ GV, $R = 1.92$ GV and $R = 1.71$ GV. As expected, the largest and smallest variation amplitudes during the period are at the lowest ($R = 1.71$ GV) and highest ($R = 2.97$ GV) rigidity, respectively. The figure shows a good correlation between the count rates of **SSD F** and the measured **AMS** sum of proton and helium fluxes $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for all rigidities.

In order to search for the best match in rigidity for which the variation for **SSD F** and $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ are the same, we show in Fig. 10 the count rate ratios in **SSD F** aboard **SOHO** to $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for rigidities $R_{low} = 1.71$ GV to $R_{low} = 3.4$ GV, respectively. From top to bottom the curves are for $R = 2.97$ GV, $R = 2.67$ GV, $R = 2.4$ GV, $R = 2.15$ GV, $R = 1.92$ GV and $R = 1.71$ GV. For rigidities below $R \leq 1.92$ the

Figure 8: The upper panel shows the time series of daily averaged count rates obtained by [SSD F](#) aboard [SOHO](#) using quiet time periods (for details see text). The middle panels display the proton and helium flux measured by [AMS-02](#) at a rigidity $R = 2.15$ GV and the lower panel the variation of the modulation potential given by [Väisänen et al. \(2023\)](#).

Figure 9: Count rate of **SSD F** aboard **SOHO** as function of the sum of the proton and helium fluxes $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for rigidities $R_{low} = 1.71$ GV to $R_{low} = 2.97$ GV. Curves are from left to right for $R = 2.97$ GV, $R = 2.67$ GV, $R = 2.4$ GV, $R = 2.15$ GV, $R = 1.92$ GV and $R = 1.71$ GV (for details see text in Sec.2.1.6.)

Figure 10: Count rate ratio of **SSD F** aboard **SOHO** and sum of the proton and helium fluxes $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for rigidities $R_{low} = 1.71$ GV to $R_{low} = 3.4$ GV, respectively. Curves are from top to bottom for $R = 2.97$ GV, $R = 2.67$ GV, $R = 2.4$ GV, $R = 2.15$ GV, $R = 1.92$ GV and $R = 1.71$ GV (for details see text in Sec.2.1.6.)

Table 1: AMS energy Ranges for Protons and Helium from Aguilar et al. (2023a) used in our analysis.

R_{low} / GV	R_{up} /GV	$E_{low,p}$ / GeV	$E_{up,p}$ / GeV	$E_{low,He}$ / (GeV/amu)	$E_{up,He}$ / (GeV/amu)
1.71	1.92	1.0122	1.1987	0.3328	0.4060
1.92	2.15	1.1987	1.4075	0.4060	0.4908
2.15	2.40	1.4075	1.6386	0.4908	0.5875
2.40	2.67	1.6386	1.8918	0.5875	0.6962
2.67	2.97	1.8918	2.1764	0.6962	0.8213
2.97	3.29	2.1764	2.4829	0.8213	0.9588

ratio is higher for lower than for higher AMS fluxes and vice versa for rigidities above $R \geq 2.15$ GV. The amplitude differences in the rigidity range vary from a factor of more than 1.2 to values smaller than 1.05 with a trend of larger amplitudes for lower rigidities. The figure also indicates that no single rigidity value results in a constant ratio of 1.0 throughout the entire period. This is detailed in the six panels of Fig. 11. All panels show the normalized ratios r_N of SSD F c_{SSD-F} as function of $(\Phi_p + \Phi_{He})(R_{low})$ together with a fit to $y = a + b \cdot x + c \cdot x^2$. The fit parameters are given in the inlet of each panel together with the correlation coefficient (C.C.) and the variance. Note, that the correlation coefficient is first negative for $R \leq 2.15$ GV and positive for $R \geq 2.4$ GV. The variance has a minimum at $R = 2.15$ GV and is increasing toward lower and higher rigidities. Thus we conclude that the best approximation of the SSD F counter for $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ is $R = R_{eff} = 2.15$ GV, with R_{eff} the effective rigidity of the single counter. A closer inspection of the panels shows that the ratio r_N remains constant for high count rates c_{SSD-F} for $R_{low} = 1.71$ GV, while the overall amplitude is best approximated by $R_{low} = 2.15$ GV.

Fig. 12 shows from top to bottom the Flux $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for $R_{low} = \{1.71, 1.92, 2.15\}$ GV. The count rate c_{SSD-F} is normalized to the fluxes. As expected, the efficient rigidity changes from solar minimum to solar maximum from lower rigidities to higher ones because low-rigidity particles are stronger suppressed in the course of the solar cycle.

Analysis with background subtraction: Fig. 11 shows a systematic trend of the normalized ratio. For the optimal rigidities of $R = 2.15$ GV and $R = 2.4$ GV a minimum at $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He} \approx 600 / (\text{m}^2 \text{ s sr GeV})$ is observed. Such a minimum may be caused by a constant GCR background. This is supported by AMS 2 studies on solar modulation of cosmic-ray protons that indicate that modulation effects are significant at rigidities up to approximately 30–50 GV. Beyond this range, the effects of solar modulation diminish, and the cosmic-ray flux approaches its interstellar (unmodulated) value (Potgieter & Vos 2017; Cholis et al. 2022; Cholis & McKinnon 2022). Therefore, a single detector counter like SSD F would measure a constant background. Fig. 16 shows in the upper panel the ratio of (SSD F-2034)/ $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ at $R = 1.71$ GV and in the lower panel the flux of $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ at $R = 1.71$ GV together with the normalized count rate of (SSD F-2034). In comparison to Fig. 12 the time period is extended into the rising and peak phase of spacecraft (SC) 24 from 2011 to 2015. In order to find the best match rigidity Fig. 14 shows the same ratio as function of $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for rigidities from 1.71 GV to 2.15 GV. The count rate c_0 that is subtracted from c_{SSDF} is determined by fitting

$$y = c_{SSDF} - c_0 = a + b \cdot (\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}) \quad (2)$$

to the ratio. The optimal value c_0 is when $|b|$ is minimal. The variance is also computed and is $Var = \{0.0129, 0.0227, 0.0275\}$ for $R = \{1.71, 1.95, 2.15\}$ GV. Note, that for rigidities above 2.4 GV c_0 becomes negative. Since the variance is increasing monotonously with rigidity the optimal value cannot be determined for the total flux $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$. In order to investigate the dependence for lower rigidities

Figure 11: Normalized ratio $r_N = \frac{c_{SSD-F}}{\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}}(R_{low})$. The correlation coefficient C.C and the fit parameter of a quadratic fit are shown in the inlets of each panel. The panels show from left to right and to to bottom the ratios for $R_{low} = \{1.71, 1.92, 2.15, 2.4, 2.67, 2.97\}$. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.

Figure 12: From top to bottom normalized count rates of EPHIN aboard SOHO to the sum of fluxes of protons and helium for rigidities at 1.71 GV, 1.92 GV and 2.15 GV measured by AMS-2 (for details see text in Sec.2.1.6).

Figure 13: From top to bottom are shown the ratio of $(SSD\ F-2034)/\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ at $R = 1.71\ GV$ and the flux of $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ and the normalized count rate of $(SSD\ F-2034)$ from 2011 to 2019. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.

Figure 14: Ratio $r = \frac{c_{SSD-F} - c_0}{\phi_p + \Phi_{He}}(R_{low})$. c_0 is given in the title of each panel. The panels show from left to right and to to bottom the ratios for $R_{low} = \{1.71, 1.92, 2.15\}$. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.

we redo the same analysis using the proton flux for the rigidities $R = \{1.0, 1.16, 1.33, 1.51, 1.71\}$ GV. The corresponding results are $c_0 = \{3908, 3417, 2845, 2214, 1463, 591\}$ /(counts/minute) with $Var = \{0.0133, 0.0072, 0.0055, 0.0082, 0.0227, 0.0547\}$. In contrast to the analysis using $\phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ we find a minimum of the variance for $R = 1.33$ GV. Fig. 16 shows for this rigidity the ratio as function of time in the upper panel. The lower panel displays the flux Φ_p and the normalized count rate $c_{SSD-F} - c_0$. Thus the single counter SSD F is a good proxy to study the galactic cosmic ray modulation of protons at a rigidity of 1.33 GV corresponding to an energy of about 700 MeV.

Figure 15: Ratio $r = \frac{c_{SSD-F} - c_0}{\phi_p}(R_{low})$. c_0 is given in the title of each panel. The panels show from left to right and to to bottom the ratios for $R_{low} = \{1.0, 1.16, 1.33, 1.51, 1.71, 1.92\}$. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.

Figure 16: From top to bottom are shown the ratio of $(SSD\ F-2846)/\Phi_p$ at $R = 1.33\ GV$ and the flux of Φ_p and the normalized count rate of $(SSD\ F-2846)$ from 2011 to 2019. For details see text in Sec.2.1.6.

During the time period from 2015 to 2019 and 2011 to 2019 the **SOHO EPHIN** count rates c_{SSDF} of **SSD-F** and $c_{SSDF} - c_0$, with c_0 optimized are compared to the flux of protons and helium and to proton only at rigidities between 1.71 GV and 2.97 GV and 1.0 GV to 2.97 GV, respectively. For the amplitude of the variation over the full cycle we find a good agreement when using the sum of the proton and helium flux at a rigidity of 2.15 GV and 1.71 GV, respectively. Utilizing the proton flux only an optimum is found for $R = 1.33$ GV when using $c_{SSDF} - c_0$. Thus the single counter **SSD F** is a good proxy to study the galactic cosmic ray modulation of protons at a rigidity of 1.33 GV corresponding to an energy of about 700 MeV.

Comparison of EPHIN aboard SOHO and Chandra Fig. 17 displays in the left and right part the normalized count rate of SSD-F aboard SOHO $c_{SSD-F,SOHO}$ and Chandra $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$ and in the lower panel the ratio of $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$ to $c_{SSD-F,SOHO}$, respectively. The normalization was performed during solar minimum in 2009. The averaged SSD-F count rates were $c_{0,SOHO} \approx 11000$ counts / minute and $c_{0,Chandra} \approx 12400$ counts / minute for EPHIN aboard SOHO and Chandra respectively. The left and the

Figure 17: The left and right panel show in the upper panels the normalized count rate of SSD-F aboard SOHO $c_{SSD-F,SOHO}$ and Chandra $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$ and in the lower panel the ratio of $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$ to $c_{SSD-F,SOHO}$, respectively. The left and the right panel are identical for time periods before 2005.3 and after 2008 (for details see text in Sec.2.1.6).

right panel are identical for time periods before 19 April 2005 (i.e. 2005.3) and after 2008. The period between 2005.3 and 2008 are influenced by the fact that SSD-A and the anti-coincidence scintillator G got noisy and were switched of in 2008. Therefore we are omitting this time period in our analysis. Although the ratio shown in the lower panel of Fig. 17 show large scatter for each period, a trend in the ratio is seen by an increasing ratio with decreasing count rates. Fig. 18 shows the normalized ratio of $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$

Figure 18: Ratio of $c_{SSD-F,Chandra}$ to $c_{SSD-F,SOHO}$ as function of the average count rate $c_{av} = (c_{SSD-F,SOHO} + c_{SSD-F,Chandra})/2$ (for details see text).

to $c_{SSD-F,SOHO}$ as function of the average count rate $c_{av} = (c_{SSD-F,SOHO} + c_{SSD-F,Chandra})/2$. The first and second period from 1999 to 2005.3 and from 2008 to 2012 are given by the blue and green dots respectively. It is important to note that the ratios for the overlapping count rates agree well with each other indicating that omitting the time period with the noisy SSD-A and the anti-coincidence shield G does not influence our analysis. While the ratio between Chandra and SOHO $r_{C/S} = 1$ during solar minimum it increases to about $r_{C/S} = 1.03$ for solar maximum. Thus the amplitude of the count rate in SSD F aboard Chandra over the solar cycle is smaller than the one aboard SOHO. The response function for protons shown in Fig. 2 by the green and red curve for SOHO and Chandra, respectively, differ at low and high energies. This difference leads to the small difference reported above.

During the time period from 1999 to 2005 and 2008 to 2012 the count rate of SSD-F of EPHIN aboard Chandra is compared to the ones of EPHIN aboard SOHO. From solar maximum in 2000 to solar minimum in 2009 the count rate increased by a factor of about 3 at both spacecraft. Normalizing the Chandra measurements to the one at SOHO we find a difference in the ratio by a factor of 1.02.

2.2 SoIo EPD HET

SoIo is an [ESA](#) mission with an orbit which will take it both close to the Sun and to high latitudes. Among other instruments, it carries a magnetometer ([Horbury et al. 2020](#)) and Solar Wind Analyser (SWA) ([Owen et al. 2020](#)) to measure in situ magnetic field and plasma properties, as well as the EPD ([Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020](#)) to measure suprathermal and energetic particles. Of particular interest is the HET instrument as part of the EPDs suite, a particle telescope covering the high-energy end of the solar energetic particle spectrum as well as SEPs, was found suitable to observe FDs (?). SoIo in situ plasma and magnetic field data are available as a low latency or high-level data product (with some delay) from the public repository [ESA Solar Orbiter Archive \(SOAR\)](#), while EPD data are available from [Christian-Albrechts-Universität \(CAU\)](#), as well as from [SOAR](#).

2.2.1 The HET Instrument

HET was designed to cover the high energy range for electrons, protons and also for several heavy ion species from $E \approx 7$ MeV/nuc to $E \approx 500$ MeV/nuc for ions that stop in the sensor head ([Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020](#)). Two Electron Proton Telescope (EPT)-HET units, FMO1 and FMO2, are mounted on the Solar Orbiter spacecraft with FMO1 looking in sun/antisun direction along the average Parker spiral and and FMO2 pointing out of the ecliptic. The location of these units is illustrated in Fig. 19.

Figure 19: Location of the EPD instrument on the SoIo spacecraft. The X-axis of the coordinate system points towards the Sun. On the left hand side the -Y panel of the spacecraft is shown with the SupraThermal Ion Spectrograph (SIS), SupraThermal Protons and alpha (STEP) and EPT-HET FMO1 units. On the +Y side only the EPT - HET FMO2 is located

Each HET instrument consists of 4 SSDs of $300 \mu\text{m}$ thickness, which are symmetrically arranged around a BGO scintillation detector that allows particles to be detected from two directions. The entrance SSDs, named HET-A, feature 2 segments, while the two inner SSDs, named HET-B, feature three segments. Segmentation enables an adjustment of the geometric factors as well as a trajectory analysis of detected particles. The outermost segment of the HET-B detectors is used as a guard ring. Particles passing through this segment do not enter the instrument through the entrance window or were scattered inside the telescope and thus are neglected. In order to stop highly energetic heavy particles and thus achieve the required energy range, BGO was chosen as the scintillation material for the HET-C detector.

Figure 20: Schematic diagram of the HET sensor head. Exemplary particle trajectories ending up in different data products are shown by the arrows: stopping in B (red), stopping in C (green), penetrating (blue), GCR channel (aquamarine), C single counter (orange). From (?)

The scintillation crystal is hexagonal with a thickness and edge length of 2 cm whose scintillation light is readout by two photodiodes placed on opposing sides (see [Elftmann \(2020\)](#) for further details).

Figure 20 shows a sketch of the HET instrument with exemplary particle trajectories for different coincidence conditions. Of special interest due to their large geometric factors for the highly energetic particles studied within SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD) are the so called GCR trigger channels shown in aquamarin, requiring a coincidence of only the inner or middle B segments and the C detector, and the single detector counters shown in orange. Both come with two subchannels, which are detailed in the subsequent section.

2.2.2 GEANT simulations of the HET

The GEANT-4 model has been developed implementing all distances and dimensions of the instrument from the CAD data, which was used for the manufacturing of the individual parts of the instrument (see Figure 31 in [Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. \(2020\)](#) for a picture of the Computer Aided Design (CAD) model). The simulation includes the electronic box of the EPT-HET unit and a fully equipped sensor head. The main importance for the HET simulation, is the correct implementation of the sensor head components including the distances and dimensions of the collimator and the detectors.

GEANT models of the High Energy Telescope (HET): Here of special interest is the so called GCR trigger. As Fig. 20 illustrates the trigger conditions and a possible trajectory of a particle counted in the GCR channel, a particle is counted in the channel if a coincidence in the inner segments of the two B detectors and a signal in the BGO-crystal is present. Note that a preliminary simulation was already performed by ?. The spacecraft was modeled as a cuboid with the size of the main body (2.20 m x 1.81 m x 1.46 m) and a total mass of 1700 kg (which corresponds to the launch mass of Solar Orbiter, excluding its solar panels). Its composition was assumed to be 200 kg of hydrazine fuel, 750 kg of aluminum, representing the structural components of the spacecraft, and 750 kg of a printed circuit board (PCB)-like material, representing the electronics components of the spacecraft and its payload. Only protons between 5 MeV and 100 GeV were used as input particles to reduce the complexity of the simulation setup, since protons comprise 90 % of primary GCR particles.

The modified GEANT model consists of the HET sensor head, the electronic box, and a simplified spacecraft model. The sensor head and the electronic box hereby remained unchanged as their dimensions and composition were already implemented according to the CAD drawings. The main focus was set on the implementation of a simplified spacecraft model to allow investigating the influence of Helium and heavy particles on the response of the GCR-trigger (for details see upcoming deliverable D2.3).

Here we followed a similar approach to EPHIN as discussed above in Section 2.1.3. The spacecraft

Figure 21: GEANT4 visualization of the HET sensor head surrounded by the spacecraft model of SoIO in the model introduced by ? and this work in the left and right panel, respectively.

model used in ? was used to determine the density a particle would see from a given trajectory on a spherical shell of a given radius and thickness. The composition and overall mass follow the spacecraft model introduced by ?. Figure 21 visualizes the two different implementations of the GEANT4 model of HET with the old and new in the left and right panels, respectively. The individual densities of each shell segment are color coded, highlighting the directionality of the surrounding passive matter by the spacecraft. The electronics box was hidden in the right panel for clarity. The simulation results for the updated GEANT4 model are available for protons, alpha particles, and electrons in the energy range between 1 MeV and 100 GeV and will be reported in deliverable 2.3.

Comparison of GEANT-4 simulations:

Results: Figure 22 shows the respective response functions for the single detector counter that measures the signal in the BGO without any further coincidence condition. The single detector counter provides two channels that are defined by the energy loss thresholds at 4 MeV and 10 MeV indicated in what follows by HG and LG respectively. For comparison, the simulations were performed with and without the spacecraft model indicated by the different colors in each panel of the figure: It can be seen that the response functions for each species follow roughly the same shape, with the main differences in the low energy cutoff, where electrons can be measured just above the thresholds, whereas the response functions for protons and alpha particles start to rise at 12 and 45 MeV, respectively, for the energy loss threshold of 4 MeV. Toward higher energies, the production of secondary particles in the spacecraft results in an increase of the response functions. This effect is especially profound for alpha particles and electrons, showing a response $\approx 2x$ that of protons at 100 GeV.

Figure 23 shows preliminary simulation results of the GCR trigger for protons, alpha particles, and electrons. Again, two channels are given by energy loss intervals in the BGO between 15 to 30 MeV and 30 to 56 MeV, respectively. These channels are indicated GCR-0 and GCR-1, respectively. As can be seen, the GCR trigger are predominantly sensitive to protons where the response remains close to the analytical geometry factor marked as black dashed horizontal line at energies above the cutoff at ≈ 140 MeV. The two response functions of the channels intersect at 350 MeV. The increase in the response functions of alpha particles and electrons due to the spacecraft appears to be negligible at this point.

Figure 22: Preliminary simulation results for single detector response functions of protons, alphas and electrons for detection thresholds of 4 and 10 MeV deposited in the BGO with and without spacecraft model.

Figure 23: Preliminary simulation results for GCR trigger response functions of protons, alphas and electrons in two channels of 15 to 30 and 30 to 56 MeV deposited in the BGO with and without spacecraft model. The horizontal dashed line marks the analytical geometry factor. For clarity the legend, valid for all panels, is only shown in the middle panel.

2.2.3 Comparison to other spacecraft measurements

In section 2.1.6 EPHIN measurements of its single counter SSD F from 2011-2019 were compared to differential channels measured by AMS-02 during the same period for quiet time periods. The comparison was performed by two different methods. The first was to use the single counter SSD F to find an efficient rigidity using flux $\Phi_p + \Phi_{He}$ for different rigidities provided by Aguilar et al. (2023a). The second was to subtract a constant background and redo the same analysis for the background subtracted flux. As expected we found a lower efficient rigidity for the background subtracted flux ($R_{eff} = 1.33$ GV for protons and $R_{eff} = 1.71$ GV for the sum of protons and helium) as for the "raw" count rates ($R_{eff} = 2.15$ GV). For details see section 2.1.6.

We now compare HET single counter and GCR trigger measurements beginning in early 2020 with the start of SolO until 2025 to those of SOHO/EPHIN. Although SolO is not located at 1 AU close to Earth the radial gradient for above 50 MeV particles was found to be less than 7%/AU (Marquardt & Heber 2019). Thus, systematic effects due to the spacecraft radial distance are small compared to other effects like FDs from CMEs and Corotating Interaction Regions (CIRs). However, the amplitudes of these effects are regularly below 10%.

Figure 24 shows an overview of the daily average count rates of the various channels of FMO1 over the mentioned time span. The corresponding plots for FMO2 are shown in the appendix in Fig. 29 to 33. To be able to compare measurements under quiet time conditions, we applied a simple filter that utilized

scipys find_peak method to automatically detect and remove SEP-events. These curves are overplotted by different colors in each panel.

Figure 24: Countrates of HET FMO1 from early 2020 until 2025. **a)** HET single detector counter HG original data (blue) and quiet times (red). **b)** HET single detector counter LG original data (blue) and quiet times (orange). **c)** comparison of quiet times measurement of HET and SOHO/EPHIN single detector counters. **d)** HET GCR-trigger 0 HG original data (blue) and quiet times (purple). **e)** HET GCR-trigger 1 original data (blue) and quiet times (magenta). **f)** comparison of quiet times measurements of HET GCR trigger and SOHO/EPHIN single detector counter.

Panels a) to c) show in the two upper panels the count rates of the single counter for **HG** and **LG** respectively. The blue curves represent the original data with multiple **SEP** events visible. The filtered time profiles are shown in red for **HG** and orange for **LG** and are compared in panel c) to the **SOHO/EPHIN SSD F** measurements shown in green. The time profiles resemble each other, with a fairly stable count rate until 2022, which then gradually decreases as the solar activity increases. The countrate measured by **EPHIN** is ≈ 3 times larger than the ones measured by the two **HET** channels, as expected by the ≈ 3 times larger geometric factor. Details are discussed below.

Panels d) to f) show in the first two panels the count rates of the single counter for **GCR-1** and **GCR2** counter, respectively. The blue and purple curves show the time profiles including and excluding **SEP** events. Panel F shows the quiet time count rates scaled to the **SSD F** ones. As for the **BGO** counters the same time profiles are measured with **SSD F** and **GCR-1** show the lowest and highest modulation amplitude from 2020 to 2025. The short-term variations in the **GCR-0** at solar minimum are correlated with temperature variations of the **HET**. Therefore, the temperature was stabilized in February 2022.

In what follows we will discuss the comparison in more detail:

Comparison of the LG and HG channels with SSD F: The left panel of Figure 25 shows the daily averaged countrates of the **HG** channel of **HET FMO1** plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of **SOHO/EPHIN** during quiet time conditions. It can be seen that the single counters are highly correlated with a Pearson-r of 0.99 and only minor uncertainties in the fit parameters.

Figure 25: Left: daily averaged countrates of the **HG** channel of **HET FMO1** plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of **SOHO/EPHIN** during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of **HET/EPHIN SSD-F** over **SSD-F**.

The right panel of the figure shows the ratios **HG/SSD F** as function of the count rate c_{SSDF} . The ratio was fitted by $HG/SSD F = A + B \cdot c_{SSDF}$. It can be seen that the ratio is fairly stable with variations of a few percent showing only a minor tendency to increase with higher countrates of **EPHIN SSD-F**. This is most likely due to shielding by the **SOHO** spacecraft, which restricts low-energy particles to entering primarily from the front. On **SoLo** the **HET** is mounted such a way that both viewing cones from the front and back are not obscured by the spacecraft.

The **LG** single counter (not shown) draws a similar picture with the only difference being a slightly reduced ratio. The linear fit parameters of the relation between the **HET** channels and **EPHIN SSD-F** are

		single HG	single LG	GCR-0*	GCR-1
FMO1	Slope	0.35	0.3	$1.28 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$0.58 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	Interception	-68.81 ± 10.98	-99.97 ± 9.42	-2.46 ± 0.05	-2.28 ± 0.03
FMO2	Slope	0.35	0.31	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$0.63 \cdot 10^{-3}$
	Interception	-4 ± 13.29	-144.83 ± 11.29	-1.27 ± 0.05	-2.5 ± 0.03

Table 2: Linear fit parameters for cross calibration of the two HET instruments and SOHO/EPHIN. Given are the values for the two single detector channels and the two GCR channels respectively. Uncertainties of the slopes are neglected.

*Values calculated for GCR-0 channel for FMO 1 are given for temperatures $> -10^\circ$.

collected in table 2 for both instrument units.

During the time period from 2020 to 2025 the count rates of SSD-F of EPHIN aboard SOHO are compared to the LG and HG counter of the BGO of HET aboard SoHO. From solar minimum in 2020 to solar maximum in 2025 the count rate decreased by a factor of about 3 at both spacecraft. Differences in the ratio by a factor of less than 0.1 are found which is in good agreement with the expected influence of the different response functions (see Fig. 2 and 22).

Comparison of the GCR-0 channel with SSD F: While the GCR-0 counter measures protons above a threshold energy of 350 MeV the GCR-1 counter can be seen as a differential channel and thus the latter would be ideally suited to compare to AMS when the data become available.

In what follows, we first compare the quiet time count rate of the integral proton channel GCR-0 with SSD F in the upper left and right panel of Fig. 26. The right panel differs from the left one such that a temperature threshold of $T \geq -10^\circ$ is taken into account. The large variation at solar minimum can be attributed to the temperature changes below that threshold as shown in more detail in Fig. 27. In the figure, both HET units are shown. While the temperature at unit 2 is always above -10° the one at HET unit 1 shows periods with $T \leq -10^\circ$. For these periods the count rate is correlated with the temperature. The reason for this effect is unknown and needs to be investigated in the future. When excluding these periods a very good correlation is found.

Comparisons of the GCR-1 channel: the GCR-1 counter can be seen as a differential channel, and thus the latter would be ideally suited to compare to AMS when the data become available. However, Fig. 28 compares in the left panel the SSD-F with the GCR-1 counter. We find a good correlation with a Pearson coefficient of 0.98. However, when plotting the count rate ratio of both channels as a function of the count rate of SSD-F, a large increase in the ratio of a factor of 4 towards a higher higher count rates in SSD-F. This dependence allows us to determine the rigidity-dependent variation in the GCR flux on intermediate time scales. However, details and the corresponding rigidity dependence can only be obtained in a direct comparison with AMS-02.

Figure 26: Top left: daily averaged countrates of the GCR-0 channel of HET FMO1 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Top right: same but times excluded where $T < -10C^\circ$. Bottom panels: respective ratios.

Figure 27: Daily averaged countrate of the GCR-0 channel in purple and temperature of the HET instrument in black. Solid lines show FMO1 and dotted lines FMO2. For clarity 2 counts/minute were added to FMO2.

Figure 28: The left panel of the figure displays the count rate in GCR-1 as function of SOHO/EPHIN. The right panel displays the ratio of GCR-1/SSD-F over SSD-F.

During the time period from 2020 to 2025 the count rates of the **GCR-0** and **GCR-1** counter are compared to the **SSD F** counter. From solar minimum in 2020 to solar maximum in 2025 the count rate decreased by a factor of about 3, 6, and 10 for the **SSD F**, **GCR-0** and **GCR-1** counter, respectively. Differences in the ratio of the **GCR-0** to **SSD F** counter are found, but small compared to the differences in the **GCR-1** to **SSD F** ratio that changes by a factor of 4. This is in good agreement with the expectations because of the very different energy response of the counters.

3 Conclusions

Single-count rate measurements from SOHO and Chandra EPHIN as well as from SoHO HET offer the possibility of investigating cosmic-ray activity on short time scales. However, in order to gain insight into, for example, the modulation of Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCRs) these counters need to be calibrated against differential measurements from spectrometers like Alpha Magnet Spectrometer (AMS) 2.

This report, which constitutes **deliverable 3.2** of the SPEARHEAD project, describes the method for the "calibration". In a first step SOHO EPHIN has been successfully compared to AMS 02: During the time period 2015 to 2019 and 2011 to 2019 the SOHO EPHIN count rates c_{SSDF} of SSD-F and $c_{SSDF} - c_0$, with c_0 optimized are compared to the flux of protons and helium and to proton only at rigidities between 1.71 GV and 2.97 GV and 1.0 GV to 2.97 GV, respectively. For the amplitude of the variation over the full cycle we find a good agreement when using the sum of the proton and helium flux at a rigidity of 2.15 GV and 1.71 GV, respectively. Using the proton flux, only an optimum is found for $R = 1.33$ GV when using $c_{SSDF} - c_0$. Thus the single counter SSD F is a good proxy for studying the modulation of galactic cosmic rays of protons at a rigidity of 1.33 GV corresponding to an energy of about 700 MeV.

In a second step, we use SOHO EPHIN as the one to compare with. We found:

EPHIN aboard Chandra: During the time period 1999 to 2005 and 2008 to 2012 the count rate of SSD-F of EPHIN aboard Chandra is compared to the ones of EPHIN aboard SOHO. From solar maximum in 2000 to solar minimum in 2009 the count rate increased by a factor of about 3 at both spacecraft. Normalizing the Chandra measurements to the one at SOHO we find a difference in the ratio by a factor of 1.02.

HET aboard SoHO: During the time period from 2020 to 2025 the count rates of the HG and LG single detector counters as well as the GCR-0 and GCR-1 counter are compared to the SSD-F of EPHIN aboard SOHO. All channels are highly correlated with the HG and LG channels showing variations in the ratio of less than 10%.

From solar minimum in 2020 to solar minimum in 2025 the count rate decreased by a factor of about 3, 6, and 10 for the single detector counter, GCR0 and GCR1 counter, respectively. Differences of $\approx 20\%$ in the ratio of the GCR-0 to SSD-F are found indicating that on short terms both counters measure nearly the same variation. This is different when comparing the GCR-1 to LG ratio that changes by a factor of 4. This is in good agreement with the expectations because of the very different energy response of the counters. However, a detailed analysis beyond a 20% accuracy needs to await the publication of the AMS fluxes.

Thus, we conclude that the single detector count rate accuracy for the missions involved in this study is comparable to AMS differential channel within an uncertainty of about 10% as determined by SOHO EPHIN.

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Appendix

This appendix displays the analogous plots of SoHO/HET FMO 2, not shown in the analysis performed in Sec.2.2.3. Linear fit parameters are summarized for both instrument units in table 2.

Figure 29: Countrates of HET FMO2 from early 2020 until 2025. **a)** HET single detector counter HG original data (blue) and quiet times (red). **b)** HET single detector counter LG original data (blue) and quiet times (orange). **c)** comparison of quiet times measurement of HET and SOHO/EPHIN single detector counters. **d)** HET GCR-trigger 0 HG original data (blue) and quiet times (purple). **e)** HET GCR-trigger 1 original data (blue) and quiet times (magenta). **f)** comparison of quiet times measurements of HET GCR trigger and SOHO/EPHIN single detector counter.

Figure 30: Left: daily averaged countrates of the HG channel of HET FMO2 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F.

Figure 31: Left: daily averaged countrates of the LG channel of HET FMO2 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F.

Figure 32: Left: daily averaged countrates of the GCR-0 channel of HET FMO2 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F.

Figure 33: Left: daily averaged countrates of the GCR-1 channel of HET FMO2 plotted versus the daily averaged countrates of SOHO/EPHIN during quiet time conditions. Linear fit shown in red with fit parameters given in the legend. Right: ratio of HET/EPHIN SSD-F over SSD-F.